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California State University, Fullerton
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REFINING THE CRITICAL OBSTETRICAL DEBRIEFING PROCESS: A QUALITY
IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Pregnancy-related deaths and other significant untoward pregnancy-related complications are not only devastating for the family but also for every healthcare team member involved in the tragedy. When this type of event occurs, emotional support for those present can be provided through debriefings (Rivera-Chiauzzi et al., 2016). Critical obstetrical incidents (COI) can cause burnout (BO), secondary traumatic stress (STS), and compassion fatigue (CF), all of which can lead to high turnover among nurses (Kelly et al., 2017). Healthcare organizations seek to identify the reasons that lead to compassion fatigue, staffing issues, and unattended emotional stress, since they have been identified as key contributors for nurses leaving their positions (Flynn, 2017; Kelly, et al., 2017). The goal of debriefing is to lessen the psychological impact after a traumatic event, discuss normal reactions to these types of events, and assist with adaptive functioning (Rivera-Chiauzzi et al., 2016). The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to revise and pilot a modified COI debriefing process to improve compassion satisfaction and decrease compassion fatigue. The aims of this project were to identify the barriers to completing the debriefing process; obtain nurses' baseline levels of compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue and secondary traumatic stress; revise the existing debriefing process; and implement and evaluate the use of a revised debriefing process.

Keywords: critical obstetrical incidents, compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, secondary traumatic stress, burnout, debriefing, and Professional Quality of Life 5.

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Background

Maternal deaths, including those that occur during a pregnancy, after a pregnancy has ended, and up to 42 days after delivery; doubled between 1987 and 2015. (Hoyert & Miniño, 2020). Furthermore, the United States' maternal mortality rate is reported to be 17.4 per 100,000 live births by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (Hoyert & Miniño, 2020). The death of a mother or a newborn can be an unbearable loss and can cause intense grief (Foreman, 2014). Infant loss is defined as the unexpected loss of a pregnancy before term or during birth, and can be due to prematurity, birth defects or other health conditions (March of Dimes, 2020). Pregnancy related deaths or other significant untoward obstetrical complications are not only devastating for the family but also for every team member involved in the tragedy. When this type of event occurs, emotional support for those present can be provided through debriefings (Rivera-Chiauzzi et al., 2016). Maternal complications including infant deaths are called "critical incidents" which can be defined as any event that is unanticipated and creates a significant emotional impact (Caine & Bagdasarian, 2003, p. 59). There are other types of critical obstetrical incidents (COI), that can occur during pregnancy, including postpartum hemorrhage, fetal distress, uterine rupture, and shoulder dystocia (Dietz, 2009).

When a COI occurs, healthcare organizations should provide support to the healthcare providers involved in the incident. This ensures that the healthcare provider's emotional state is supported. Debriefings performed after a COI helps those involved to share their feelings, recap what has happened and describe how procedures could be changed to lead to different outcomes. When a debriefing process occurs after a COI, the leader uses this time to provide guided reflection so that those present can learn from the event, and plan for future similar situations (Shinnick et al., 2011). A debriefing process provides an opportunity for healthcare providers to

identify opportunities for team and work improvements and share coping strategies while showing mutual understanding, and empathy for one another (Dietz, 2009; Rivera-Chiauzzi et al., 2016). The debriefing tool utilized contains questions, which elicit feelings about the event, identifies key players and the timing of action taken to address it (Dietz, 2009). The goal of debriefing is to lessen the psychological impact after a traumatic event, discuss normal reactions to these types of events, and assist with adaptive functioning (Rivera-Chiauzzi et al., 2016). Overall, a debriefing tool when used effectively, is designed to help healthcare providers feel supported, less stressed and can assist in their emotional recovery (Dietz, 2009).

Significance

Critical obstetrical incidents can cause burnout, secondary trauma, and compassion fatigue, all of which can lead to high turnover among nurses (Kelly et al., 2017). Twenty percent of registered nurses leave their positions within the first year in the field, regardless of if an incident is experienced (Kelly et al., 2017). Healthcare organizations seek to identify the reasons that lead to compassion fatigue, staffing issues, and unattended emotional stress, since they have been identified as key contributors for nurses leaving their positions (Flynn, 2017; Kelly, et al., 2017). The research is limited with regards to the role critical obstetrical incidents play in nurses leaving during their first year.

When individuals experience a critical incident, they require immediate support. Swartz (2013) reported that 60% of nurses who experienced a secondary traumatic event needed immediate support, with 30% requiring follow-up, and 10% needing outside professional counseling. Unfortunately, poor communication and poor teamwork can account for 70% of COIs in obstetrical units (Committee & Committee on Patient, 2009). Therefore, the debriefing

process can help improve teamwork, assist with potential safety threats, and provide coping skills to nurses who experience critical incidents (Kessler et al., 2015).

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project took place at a regional medical center in Southern California, where more than 5,000 babies are delivered each year. At the project facility, a COI is identified by an obstetrical (OB) alert. An OB alert is an overhead alarm, heard throughout the hospital and initiated by the primary nurse or a member of the multidisciplinary team. The alert is activated, similar to a code blue, to request the presence of a physician and staff coordinator to assist. An OB alert is called for a maternal hemorrhage, maternal distress, fetal distress, eclamptic seizure, or maternal/newborn respiratory arrest.

It was found that the existing hospital's debriefing process was not consistently initiated after an OB alert and debriefings were not consistently completed, due to the fast pace and the lack of time allotted for discussion of the incident. In May, 2019, there were ten COIs at the project hospital. However, of the 10 COI's that occurred, nurses completed the established debriefing 2.5 times. The hospital used an existing debriefing form to guide the process based on the recommendations from the American Heart Association and the California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative (CMQCC).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to revise and pilot a modified COI debriefing process to improve compassion satisfaction and decrease compassion fatigue.

The aims of this project were to a) identify barriers to completing the debriefing process, b) obtain baseline levels of compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue and secondary traumatic stress c) revise the debriefing process d) evaluate the efficacy of the revised process based on

staff satisfaction, levels of compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, and adherence to the process.

Theoretical Framework

The framework used for this DNP project was the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice (See Figure 1) (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Iowa Model was developed in 1994 to guide clinicians to use research findings and apply it to patient care (Titler, et al., 2001). This model was used to develop solutions to problems identified by nurses who then incorporated successful strategies into patient care (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The purpose of the Iowa Model was to guide nurses and other members of the healthcare team in making decisions about clinical and organizational practices that affected the overall outcomes of the patients (Dang et al., 2015). The Iowa Model demonstrated the importance of including the whole healthcare system from the provider to the patient to the organization and those who were responsible for making decisions (Dontje, 2007). The seven steps of the Iowa Model are based on finding solutions for the problems identified and the scientific process used to address the problem, which made it applicable for use among multidisciplinary teams (Dang et al., 2015). This model provided a method for guiding nurses to improve patient results, improve nursing practice, and monitor the cost to the organization (Haxton et al., 2012).

The seven steps of the modified Iowa Model included the selection of a topic, forming a team, evidence retrieval, grading the evidence, developing an evidence-based practice model, implementing the evidence-based practice, and lastly, evaluation (Titler et al., 2001).

The first step was the selection of the topic (Figure 1). The first decision point encountered in the Iowa model was to identify if the topic was a priority and required change for the organization, department, or unit (Brown, 2017). The topic can be triggered from a

knowledge-focused or a problem-focused position (Brown, 2014). A knowledge-focused trigger comes from a need to change based on research or organizational standards. A problem-focused trigger is one that is identified as a clinical problem (Brown, 2014).

The second step of the Iowa Model was forming a team. The team consists of individuals who can help in the development, application, and evaluation of the evidence-based practice change (Doody & Doody, 2011). The team should be made up of participants who can provide input and support regarding the topic (Doody & Doody, 2011).

The third and fourth steps of the model are preceded by another decision point, which identifies if there is sufficient research on the topic. The third step of the model is to gather relevant research by exploring relevant electronic databases (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The fourth step determines the quality of the research gathered. This can be done by using a three-tiered grading system, which identifies usefulness, relevance, and practicability of the research (Doody, & Doody, 2011, Briggs, 2008)).

The fifth step focuses on developing an evidence-based practice standard utilizing the reviewed literature (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The sixth step is preceded by a final decision point, which determines if the change is appropriate for implementation (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Combining the new practice and sustaining the change is the last step in the Iowa model. During this step, a researcher reviews and identifies areas that need to be adjusted based on the results of the practice change (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Figure 1

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

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Integration of the Iowa Model into the DNP Project

The integration of the Iowa Model into the quality improvement project began with the following steps (Figure 2).

Step One: Identify the Problem

The first step was the selection of the topic, which was identified as the COI debriefing process. The purpose of the change was to identify the challenges to completing the debriefing process and decrease the consequences healthcare providers experienced after a COI. The debriefing process was identified as a priority after discussions with the perinatal nurse educator (PNE) who confirmed that this was an issue that needed improvement. The project facility had a debriefing process guideline in place; however, it was not being completed with every COI and different debriefing forms were being utilized. The current data indicated that there were ten COIs in May, 2019, and a complete debriefing session occurred less than three times. Upon review, it was noted that portions of the debriefing process were missing, which confirmed that an improvement was needed.

Step Two: Forming a Team

The second step of the Iowa Model was to form a team that implemented and evaluated the debriefing process. The team consisted of the Unit Director, Perinatal Nurse Educator (PNE), Staff Coordinators (SC), Charge Nurses (CN), and Registered Nurses (RN)). The project author asked both the day and the night shift staff coordinators to participate in the project. Staff Coordinators attended all COIs and collected the debriefing tool after every COI. Their participation was essential since the project author was not able to be present every day and night.

Step Three: Evidence Retrieval

The third step of the Iowa Model involved another decision point which helped to determine and identify if there was relevant research on the topic of debriefing tools. The databases searched included: CINAHL, PubMed, Psych INFO, Science Direct, Academic Search Premier EBSCO databases, OVID, and Google Scholar. The following search terms were used: “debriefing,” “critical events,” “critical obstetrical incidents,” “sentinel events,” “perinatal emergencies,” “secondary trauma stress,” “compassion fatigue,” and “burnout.” The search was limited to scholarly articles which were peer reviewed and published only in the English language from 2010 to present. There were over 100 scholarly articles found with many of them using the debriefing process as a supplement to education and not after a critical incident. Twenty-three scholarly and peer reviewed articles grades A-B and level I-III were selected. The literature review was divided into the following sections: Critical obstetrical incidents (perinatal emergencies), secondary traumatic stress, compassion fatigue, burnout, and debriefing. There was sufficient research on the topic, which caused the project author to move forward with the implementation of a new debriefing tool.

Step Four: Grading the Evidence

The research collected for the project was graded using a three-tiered grading system that evaluated the effectiveness, appropriateness, and feasibility for quantitative and qualitative research (Doody and Doody, 2011). The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines were also used for critiquing systematic reviews (Polit & Beck, 2017). The next decision point identified quality literature and then graded the evidence obtained.

Step Five: Design and Pilot the Practice Change

The third decision point in the Iowa Model asked if the change was appropriate for implementation, and the last two steps are combined into a new practice and sustainment of the change. The project continued to identify and engage key personnel and monitor for indications of quality improvement. The following step required modification of the existing process and pilot the practice change. The author obtained permission to use the Professional Quality of Life 5 scale (see Appendix C-D) and identified the different debriefing guidelines that were being used and collaborated with the PNE to consolidate all the debriefing forms (Appendix E-F) into one to be consistently used, and the pre-implementation debriefing satisfaction survey on the current practice of debriefing after COIs was administered to the staff. The ProQOL 5 scale was given to all nurses at the beginning of the project, prior to implementation of the modified debriefing process, and at the end of the four month pilot. The ProQOL 5 has been used since 1995 and measures the level of compassion satisfaction, and compassion fatigue, which is divided into two subscales: secondary traumatic stress and burnout (See Figure 3) (Stamm, 2010). The ProQOL 5 was originally known as the “Compassion Fatigue Test” and was developed by Charles Figley in the 1980’s (Stamm, 2010). The ProQOL 5 is not a diagnostic tool but is used to evaluate the balance of both positive and negative experiences (Stamm, 2010). A pre-implementation debriefing satisfaction survey was developed to identify the satisfaction of the current debriefing process among staff. The author generated reports using the number of debriefing forms completed per month in relation to the total number of COIs and a reported amount of correctly completed debriefing forms in relation to the number of completed forms over four months. The author developed a chart to show the results using data on the current practice of debriefing after COIs and a chart showing the results after the pilot had been

completed. The continued plan for this project is to evaluate the debriefing process quarterly and reinforce education as needed with staff.

Step Six: Integrate

The sixth step was preceded by the decision point, which asked if the change was appropriate for implementation. This was discussed with the PNE and was adjusted as necessary to complete the pilot in four months. The current debriefing guidelines were reviewed to modify the process for better compliance. Considerations were discussed with the PNE to assess which methods were used and were most effective. All former debriefing forms were removed, and the modified one-page debriefing form was initiated. Education was provided virtually via email to all licensed staff due to COVID 19 protocols and limited personal gatherings. Discussions regarding policy and procedures occurred to ensure sustainment of the practice change. The last step was the evaluation of the DNP project and identification of the value and contribution the practice change had on decreasing compassion fatigue through the newly modified debriefing process.

Step Seven: Sustain the Practice Change

The debriefing process will be sustained through on-going audits of the debriefing form to ensure that it is properly completed. Yearly satisfaction surveys may be used to provide more insight to the nurses' emotional well-being to the new modified process.

Figure 2

Modified Iowa Model for this Project

Review of Literature

A literature review was conducted to obtain research related to the project's purpose, which identified challenges to completing the debriefing process, critical incidents, and emotional effects on healthcare providers. The databases searched included: PubMed, Psych INFO, Google Scholar, Science Direct, Academic Search Premier EBSCO databases, OVID and CINAHL. The following search terms were used: "debriefing," "critical events," "critical obstetrical incidents," "sentinel events," "perinatal emergencies," "secondary trauma stress," "compassion fatigue," and "burnout." The search was limited to scholarly articles which were peer reviewed and published in the English language only from 2010 to present. There were over 100 scholarly articles found with many of them using the debriefing process as a supplement to education and not after a critical incident. Twenty-three scholarly and peer reviewed articles grades A-B and level I-III were selected. The literature review was divided into the following sections: Critical obstetrical incidents (perinatal emergencies), Secondary Traumatic Stress and Compassion Fatigue, Burnout, and Debriefing.

Critical Obstetrical Incidents

Individuals working in the medical field often experience repeated exposure to patient losses, injuries, or sometimes unexpected patient outcomes. These incidents create an emotional burden that healthcare professionals carry with them into their work environment (Arriaga et al., 2019; McNamara et al., 2017; Vaithilingam et al., 2008; Harrison & Wu, 2017). If healthcare providers are unable to manage using their typical coping strategies, then this can lead to psychological distress, anxiety, and distractibility (Caine & Bagdasarian, 2003; Vaithilingam et al., 2008). This experience can be overwhelming, preventing the healthcare providers from engaging in their job duties. Despite training in multiple areas of emergency responses,

healthcare professionals are not always capable of processing the incident that occurred without support (Foreman, 2014). Healthcare professionals in the obstetrics department are under an added stress of working with new mothers and their unborn or recently born babies. An unexpected COI in the perinatal department can be fetal distress, umbilical cord prolapses, shoulder dystocia, maternal hemorrhage, and uterine rupture, which can result in fetal or maternal death (Corbett et al., 2012; Caine & Bagdasarian, 2003). This creates an added emotional burden that is unique to the perinatal department.

Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) and Compassion Fatigue (CF)

When a patient experiences a critical incident, the healthcare provider also experiences it with them, as providers may have been unable to prevent it from happening or witnessed it happen. When an adverse incident occurs, the patient is considered the first person affected, which makes her the first victim, the second victim is the person providing the care or viewing the incident, and the third victim is the organization (Swartz, 2013). Beck and Gable, (2012), argued that STS occurs because of a person witnessing or experiencing an adverse incident or medical hazard. Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) is reported to be associated with feelings of vulnerability, guiltiness, anxiety, and isolation (Beck & Gable, 2012; Kelly et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2019). Individual's experiencing STS can also suffer from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in the same manner as an individual who experienced the trauma (Beck & Gable, 2012). Another definition of STS arises from helping and wanting to assist someone who is traumatized by an event or is suffering (Beck, 2011; Bride et al., 2004).

Compassion fatigue (CF) can be divided into two parts, which are secondary traumatic stress (STS) and burnout (BO). Compassion fatigue is the result of extended length of exposure to trauma leading to physical or mental symptoms (Meadors & Lamson, 2008). The term CF has

been used instead of STS because it is considered a friendlier term but is interchangeable (Beck, 2011). The area's most often identified by nurses leading to compassion fatigue were work, personal and patient related situations (Markwell et al., 2016). The mixed methods study by Beck and Gable (2012), reported their study as being the first quantitative and qualitatively study published that focused on STS in Labor and Delivery nurses. The measures used in the mixed studies were the secondary traumatic stress scale, compassion fatigue survey, and the ProQOL 5 scale.

The STS scale was developed to measure STS symptoms using a seventeen-point Likert scale and each item corresponded to one of the seventeen PTSD symptoms in the Diagnostic Statistic Manual of Mental Disorders, fourth edition (Beck, 2011). The persons then answer the questions and rate how often they have experienced the symptoms on the survey and subscales of intrusion, avoidance, and arousal (Beck, 2011). The survey correlates highly with the measure of psychological distress ($r = .83, p < .001$) (Beck, 2011). These feelings can lead to burnout, if the individuals do not receive support to address their feelings regarding the situation that started the event (Kelly et al., 2017). The ProQOL 5 survey consists of three subscales: Compassion satisfaction (CS), burnout, and secondary traumatic stress (Markwell et al., 2016). The ProQOL 5 is a 30 item instrument using a five-point Likert scale assessing how frequently the persons have experienced a particular situation at work and their identified feelings related to those events (Markwell et al., 2016). Compassion satisfaction is the degree of the positive emotions experienced when helping others and the person's ability to contribute to helping (Stamm, 2010). When a nurse experiences compassion satisfaction, he/she gains a sense of self-worth, resulting in overall gratification (Salmond et al., 2017).

Burnout

Burnout is a slow growing response to demanding situations, which mentally, emotionally, and physically drain an individual to the point of exhaustion (Reith, 2018). Burnout is caused by many work-related activities such as excessive demands of energy, time, substantial amounts of documentation, policies, and practices for job expectations (Beck, 2011; Beck & Gable, 2012; Kelly et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2019). When these activities are experienced over an extended period of time, the person may suffer from CF, and can lead to apathy (Beck, 2011; Beck & Gable, 2012; Kelly et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2019). In a study by De la Fuente-Solana et al., (2019) it was reported that nurses who assisted in births had a higher level of emotional exhaustion especially those who were younger with less experience, and the more experienced had increased depersonalization (detachment or coldness) to events which both led to burnout at a rate of 25-35% (De la Fuente-Solana et al., 2019). Those in the helping profession, such as nurses, are 40% to 85% more likely to develop CF and/or high rates of traumatic symptoms when untreated, which can lead to BO (Mathieu, 2012). Individuals suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder experience feelings of invasion, evasion, and excitement (Beck, 2011; Beck & Gable, 2012; Kelly et al., 2019). There are several surveys that have been used to measure the risk for STS, CF, and burnout, including the Secondary Stress Scale (SSS), the Compassion Fatigue Self-Test (CFST), and the Professional Quality of Life (ProQOL) scale, Maslach's burnout inventory, and the Emotional Stress Reaction Questionnaire (ESRQ) (Beck, 2011; Reith, 2018). Recommendations have been made for hospitals to continue to develop internal strategies to address the factors that lead to burnout. Debriefings have been found to effectively decrease staff stress when a critical incident occurs (Reith, 2018).

Debriefing

The purpose of a debriefing process is to provide a time and location in which staff can gain psychological closure, emotional support, and a sense of well-being after a critical incident (Vaithilingam et al., 2008). The debriefing process involves a group of people that gather in a room or designated area after a critical incident and discuss the aftermath of the event. The group uses a guided reflection tool to review the scenario and thought processes of those who were present during the incident (Corbett et al., 2012; Kessler et al., 2015; Harrison, & Wu, 2017). Using a guided reflection tool to organize the debriefing session can assist with the discussion of the incident and encourage interprofessional communication (Arriaga et al, 2019; Kleiner et al., 2014). The goal is to improve behavior, show team members support, enhance learning, and improve patient outcomes (Arriaga et al., 2019; Corbett et al., 2012; Hanson & Pian-Smith, 2017). Arriaga et al. (2019) found that when communication was limited or was not clear, and a critical incident occurred; a debriefing had not been performed. This may have been due to the unavailability of staff to debrief, which only helps to perpetuate the limited access to support that healthcare providers need to help them process the incident (Arriaga et al., 2019). This limited availability of time is a reality that must be addressed, since critical incidents happen, and time needs to be allotted to process them through a debriefing. Communication is essential in all departments of the hospital, especially in critical care areas. Therefore, steps need to be taken to enhance communication. Lack of time was noted to be one of the main reasons debriefing sessions do not occur (Arriaga, et al., 2019). The lack of time to debrief is often due to doctors, who lead the debriefing process not able to stay with staff, as they must move on to the next case (Arriaga et al., 2019; Boet et al.; Corbett et al., 2012; McNamara et al., 2017). A strategy used to address this is to train nurses on the debriefing process. Finally, providing a structured debriefing

process can assist team members and practitioners to develop strategies to decrease the risk of STS, CF, BO, and improve clinical care (Kessler et al., 2015).

In the studies by Arriaga et al. (2019), Boet et al. (2019), and McNamara et al. (2017), it was reported that not having a gold standard for debriefing may be a reason for debriefings not being completed. In the process of reviewing the literature, it was identified that there are “no published studies on the routine use of debriefing in perinatal units for critical events or related to performance” (Corbett et al., 2012, p. 572). Arriaga, et al. (2019) used a mixed study to analyze the barriers of debriefing and showed that out of the 89 events more than 50% contained communication failures, which were associated with those events not being debriefed. This information led to the questioning of whether lack of a debriefing can increase malpractice risk and compromise patient safety (Arriaga et al., 2019).

Summary

In summary, the studies reviewed showed that providing a debriefing process after a critical event helped healthcare providers heal emotionally, psychologically, and physically, while improving skills and communication. Although, there was limited literature on interventions, the few that were found had been used in multiple facilities with success. Implementing a debriefing process allowed healthcare providers to discuss emotional and psychological feelings after a COI with the support of their peers in a nonjudgmental manner.

Methods

This section describes the steps taken to revise and pilot the modified COI debriefing process and to obtain nurse's baseline measurement for compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue using the ProQOL 5. The setting for the project, inclusion criteria for the participants and a description of the design are also explained. Second, the steps taken to ensure that ethical issues were appropriately addressed are explained. The third and fourth steps were to retrieve and grade the literature on CS, CF, STS, BO, and debriefing. Lastly, the measures and procedures used to pilot and evaluate this project are described.

Setting and Sample

This quality improvement project occurred at a regional medical center in Southern California. The Women's Center has eight high risk antepartum rooms, 20 labor and delivery rooms, and 30 postpartum rooms, and 5,000 babies are delivered per year. There were 216 Labor and Delivery and Postpartum registered nurses, six clinical coordinators, two nurse practitioners (one is the author), one perinatal educator, and one unit manager participating in the project.

The sample for this quality improvement project included all licensed professionals involved with a COI, which were all Registered Nurses (RNs) and Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVNs). The sample size for obtaining the baseline data on the ProQOL 5 and then the Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction survey were 216 of the currently licensed personnel working on the unit. The OB staff was invited to participate and were able to discontinue their participation at any time. There was no financial incentive to participate in the project; however, relaxation activities were provided to members of the unit regardless of participation. There was no repercussion for non-participation in the project.

Ethical Issues

The Institutional Review Board at California State University, Los Angeles, the Chief Nursing Officer of the project facility, and the Director of the Women's Center approved the project (Appendix C). The project did not involve patient information, patient demographics, or patient care change. Confidentiality was maintained by using anonymous surveys with no identifiable information collected. All data obtained was maintained in a password protected computer and debriefing data was placed in the PNEs locked office in a locked drawer. After completing the pre-implementation ProQOL 5 survey, all participants were given information to contact the Employee Assistance Program (EAP) information if they felt they needed further support. The project facility provides an EAP counseling service free of charge to all employees. Short-term sessions are also available to address issues of anxiety, depression, and stress management to all staff.

Measures

The Professional Quality of Life 5 (ProQOL 5) assessed compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue. The ProQOL 5 assessed the positive and negative emotions experienced after a COI, and its effects on a healthcare provider's ability to care for others (Stamm, 2010). The ProQOL 5 has more than 200 peer-reviewed papers and more than 100,000 articles that have used the earlier versions of the ProQOL 5 which showed it to have good construct validity (Stamm, 2010). The Cronbach's alpha scale reliability score for Compassion Satisfaction was 0.88, 0.75 for Burnout and 0.81 for Secondary Traumatic Stress (Markwell, Polivka, Morris, and Ryan, 2016; Stamm, 2010). The inter-scale correlations show 2% shared variance with STS and 5% shared variance with BO. The shared variance between these two scales is 34%. The difference between the two scales is that BO scale does not address fear while the STS scale

does. This tool has been used across populations including social workers, health professionals, and firefighters (Stamm, 2010). The ProQOL 5 is a 30 item self-report questionnaire divided into two scales: Compassion Satisfaction (CS) and Compassion Fatigue (Stamm 2010). The Compassion Fatigue (CF) scale is further divided into two subscales: Burnout (BO), and Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) (Stamm, 2010). Each scale (CS, BO, and STS) includes 10 items which were scored on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Very Often. (Stamm, 2010) (Appendix D). The items were summed for a total score for each scale. Additionally, the individual items of each scale can be interpreted independently (Caringi et al. 2017).

Figure 3

Diagram of Professional Quality of Life 5

Note. B. Hudnall Stamm, 2009-2012. Professional Quality of Life 5: Compassion Satisfaction and Fatigue Version 5 (ProQOL). <http://www.proqol.org>.

The CS scale measured the pleasure a person derives from being able to help others. A person with low compassion satisfaction is at high risk for burnout and high risk of STS (Markwell et al., 2016). The ProQOL 5 defined the scores of 10 to 22 as low, 23 to 41 was

moderate, and a high score was 42 to 50. This range was the same for the BO and STS. The BO scale measures tiredness, frustration, anger, and depression which were related to Burnout (Stamm, 2010). Lastly, the STS scale measures negative feelings driven by fear and work-related trauma (Stamm, 2010).

The author adapted a nine-question pre-implementation and post-implementation debriefing satisfaction survey to assess possible reasons the debriefing guideline tool was being under-utilized (Laboy, 2019) (Appendix I and Appendix J). The pre-implementation survey contained seven questions related to COIs experienced using a Likert scale of five choices (all of the time, most of the time, sometimes, occasionally, and never). Two open-ended questions were included. Open-ended questions were used to identify common terms reported as barriers related to debriefing or any of the subscales related to the ProQOL 5.

Procedures and Metrics

Using the modified version of the Iowa Model, the first two phases were completed by identifying a topic, which was to modify the debriefing process and form a supporting team (Doody & Doody, 2011). The purpose of the change was to identify the challenges to completing the debriefing process and decrease the consequences healthcare providers experienced after a COI. The team consisted of the Perinatal Nurse Educator (PNE), Staff Coordinators (SC), Charge Nurses (CN), and Registered Nurses (RN)). The project author asked both the day and the night shift staff coordinators to participate in the project. Staff Coordinators attended all COIs and collected the debriefing tool after every COI. The team assisted in championing the project during initiation and implementation phase. The fifth and sixth steps continue with designing and implementing the practice change. This was completed sending out the Pre-ProQOL survey and the Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Surveys at the beginning of

the project using the Qualtrics software. The implementation period occurred over one week. After the implementation period, the currently licensed personnel (216) were sent a Post-ProQOL 5 and a Post-Implementation Satisfaction Survey. Data were collected monthly to evaluate the completion of the debriefing process.

During the beginning of the project, changes in the administrative team (Women's Center Director retired and new Director was unavailable to confirm the approval of the initiation date) were made which delayed the beginning of the project. The initial steps of the project occurred in collaboration with the PNE and included the analysis and evaluation of the COI debriefings that occurred from July, 2020, to October, 2020. This data was collected using an audit tool and evaluated for completion to identify areas of improvement. It was identified that older debriefing forms (Appendix E) were being used to complete debriefing sessions and most of the time were not fully completed. To modify the process the older forms were removed from the debriefing file and replaced with the one-page modified form (Appendix F). These audits were filed in the PNE locked office. The one-page debriefing tool was exclusively used during the months of November, 2020, and continues to be used exclusively.

The staff coordinators were informed about the project date one month prior to the planned start date while attending a staff coordinator meeting. Two project posters were created by the author and presented to the Women's Center Director and to the staff coordinators at the monthly meeting prior to sending out the Pre-Implementation Surveys (Appendix G). The two posters showed the purpose of the ProQOL 5 and common terms that were used in the surveys. Introduction of the planned project was done for the participants two weeks prior to the first surveys being sent out. Due to the COVID19 pandemic, adjustments were made regarding the dissemination of any in-person education that had been planned for the participants. Day shift

and night shift huddles were attended while maintaining social distancing, so the author could introduce the project and inform the participants about the surveys that were being distributed. These posters were displayed in the staff hallway so participants who were not in attendance during huddles could see a preview of the ProQOL 5 survey and its terms. Four weeks prior to beginning of the implementation phase, the cover letter with the invitation to participate (Appendix H) along with the Pre-Implementation ProQOL 5 Survey anonymous link provided by the Qualtrics software program was sent to all licensed personnel via facility emails. The author noted few Pre-Implementation ProQOL surveys were returned, so the survey deadline was extended for two more weeks. The Pre-Implementation Satisfaction Survey link was sent four weeks after the first survey was sent out using the anonymous link provided by the Qualtrics software program (Appendix I). Two to three reminder emails to complete the Pre-Implementation ProQOL 5 and the Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Surveys were sent out weekly until the start of the implementation phase.

Intervention

The educational sessions were provided four weeks after initial surveys were completed. Weekly meetings with the PNE were conducted to ensure debriefings were being conducted using the correct form and evaluated for completeness. The pre-implementation surveys were sent out in the same manner and was also left open for four weeks. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and restrictions on gatherings, it was decided the best mode of education would be to provide remote education. The author started with resources obtained from the ProQOL.org website. The first email sent provided an article by Laurie Barkin, RN, MS, “Nurses and Compassion Fatigue.” The following email provided both a one-page article on how to recognize compassion fatigue and another article related to steps one can take on the path to wellness. Both

found on [compassion fatigue.org](http://compassionfatigue.org). Another email included a copy of the “Bill of a Caregiver’s Rights” (Compassion Fatigue Project Awareness, 2013), a link to a TED talks video by J. Watt on “What is compassion fatigue and do you have it?” and another TED talks video by P. Smith on “How to manage compassion fatigue in caregiving” (Ted, 2017). A subsequent email followed with links to two different free applications providing activities to improve self-care and mindfulness. The first link was headspace: <https://www.headspace.com/> and the second link was for the tapping solution: <https://www.thetappingsolution.com/>. The following email was sent with a debriefing article, “Debrief in emergency departments to improve compassion fatigue and promote resiliency” by M. Schmidt explaining the importance of debriefing and its effects on nurses. Lastly, the author developed a 13 slide PowerPoint presentation that was sent via staff email summarizing the importance of CS, CF, BO, and their effects on nurses.

Weekly fifteen-minute meetings were held with the SCs to identify barriers and to collect the debriefing data collection forms. The debriefing tool identified the number of debriefings that occurred during the shift and the type of COI that occurred. The COIs were monitored for four months and the debriefing forms were categorized as completed or not completed and placed into their respective categories. This data was collected at the end of the month and compiled at the end of the project. The forms were stored in the PNE’s office along with the data collection form.

The Post-Implementation ProQOL 5 and the Post-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey link via the Qualtrics software (see Appendix J) were simultaneously emailed to all licensed staff one week after the implementation phase was completed. The Post-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Surveys assessed the impact of the modified debriefing process after a COI. To improve the response rate, two to three reminder emails were sent weekly after the

initial emailing. Time frames were adjusted due to pandemic and organizational changes. All pre- and post-data were entered into an Excel spreadsheet and the SPSS-27 software was further used to determine future interventions, and converted into a bar graph that best illustrated the data. Establishment of sustainability and discussion of necessary adjustments are planned to be conducted quarterly.

Results

The results of this QI project relate to COIs with completed debriefing sessions, the pre- and post-implementation of the ProQOL 5 and the debriefing satisfaction survey.

Critical Obstetrical Incidents Results for Pre- and Post-Implementation

Baseline data was collected four months prior to the implementation of the new debriefing tool (Figure 4). The number of debriefings and the number of COIs completed was collected from July, 2020, to October, 2020. The COIs were reviewed and evaluated for completeness of the debriefing tool. There were 22 COIs from July, 2020, through October, 2020. Upon examination of the 22 COIs, there were 19 completed debriefing tools and three that were not completed. This data provided a completion rate, prior to implementation of 86.36% (19/22) and an incompleteness rate of 13.64% (3/22). Post-implementation data was collected from November, 2020, to February, 2021 (Figure 5). There were 16 COIs from November to February. Upon examination of the completeness of the debriefing tool, only 14 were correctly completed. This data provided a completion rate of 87.5% (14/16) and an incompleteness rate of 12.5% (2/16).

Figure 4*Pre-Implementation COI (July, 2020-October, 2020)*

Note. Debriefings completed and not completed from July to October, 2020.

Figure 5*Post-Implementation COI (November, 2020 – February, 2021)*

Note. Debriefings completed and not completed from November until February, 2021.

Pre-Implementation Professional Quality of Life 5 Survey

There were 216 licensed personnel invited to participate in the pre-implementation surveys. There were three surveys that were not distributed to employees since email addresses were either deactivated or employees were on leave. Of the 213 licensed personnel who were invited to participate, 36 participants completed the Pre-Implementation ProQOL 5 Survey, for a response rate of 17%. Each scale was scored separately. The questions are divided into CS scale and two subscales which are under CF. The subscales under CD were BO and STS. The project author scored the ProQOL 5 survey using the concise ProQOL 5 2010 manual. The first step in scoring involved reversing items 1, 4, 15, 17, and 29, then summing the items by their subscale (Stamm, 2010, p 15). There are 10 pre-selected questions in each scale that are added for a total score of low, medium, or high level for each subscale. A low level was identified as a total score less than 22. A moderate level was a total score between 23 and 41. Lastly, a high level was a total score of 42 or more. Of the 36 participants who responded to the pre-implementation ProQOL 5, the CS level was recorded to be moderate, with 21 participants with a total between 23-41. The BO scale also was a low level with most responses totaling a score of less than 22. Lastly, the STS level was low with most responses also totaling a score of less than 22. The pre-implementation ProQOL 5 results are provided in Figure 6.

Figure 6

Pre-Implementation ProQOL 5 Survey: Three subscales

Note. Participants' scores on CS, BO, and STS.

Post-implementation Professional Quality of Life 5 Survey

Of the 213 licensed personnel who were invited to participate, thirty-six participants responded to the pre-ProQOL 5 survey and seven responded to the post-ProQOL 5 for the response rate of 19.4% (7/36). The results showed a high level of CS among the participants. The next subscale was BO with most participants having a low level of BO. Lastly, the STS subscale also showed the majority of participants having a low level of STS. The post-implementation ProQOL 5 results are provided in Figure 7. The results of the combined Pre and Post ProQOL 5 are provided in Figure 8.

Figure 7*Post-Implementation ProQOL 5 Survey: Three Subscales*

Note. Participants' scores on CS, BO, STS.

Figure 8*Pre- and Post-ProQOL 5 Survey Results*

Note. Pre-ProQOL 36 participants and Post-ProQOL 7 participants.

Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey

Of the 213 licensed personnel invited to participate in the pre-implementation debriefing satisfaction survey, 23 completed the survey, for a response rate of 10.8% (23/213). Descriptive statistics was used to develop the following frequency table (Table 1). The first question in the Pre-Implementation Debriefing Survey asked, “How often do you experience OB Alerts at work?” Of the twenty-three responses, eleven (47.8%) experienced an OB Alert “sometimes” or “occasionally” at work. The second question asked, “Do you feel your employer helps you cope with stress associated with OB Alerts?” Those who responded felt that their employer helped them cope “most of the time” (26.1%) with the stress associated with an OB Alert. Respondents reported that the employer offered a debriefing session after an OB Alert “sometimes/occasionally” (21.7%). The majority of the respondents reported that it is “important” (47.8%) and “very important” (13.0%) to hold a debriefing session after an OB Alert. Of those respondents who had experienced an OB Alert, 21.7% reported that the debriefing sessions were held “one to three days” (17.4%) or “immediately” (13.0%) post the OB Alert. The last question asked, “How soon should a debriefing session be held after an OB Alert?” The participants responded that a debriefing session should be held “immediately” (39.1%) or “one day after” (21.7%). Common themes related to barriers that respondents believed prevented debriefing sessions from being completed after an OB Alert were lack of time, increased acuity of patients, other patient assignments, and limited staff (Figure 9).

Table 1*Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey*

Variables	N	Frequency (Valid %)
Q-1 How often do you experience OB Alerts at work?		
No answer	9	39.0%
All the time	1	4.3%
Sometimes/Occasionally	11	47.0%
Never	2	8.7%
Q-2 Do you feel your employer helps you cope with the stress associated with OB Alerts?		
No Answer	10	43.5%
All the time	2	8.7%
Most of the time	6	26.0%
Sometimes/Occasionally	4	17.0%
Never	1	4.3%
Q-3 Does your employer offer debriefing sessions after an OB Alert?		
No answer	10	43.0%
All the time	2	8.7%
Most of the time	3	13.0%
Sometimes/Occasionally	5	21.0%
Never	3	13.0%
Q-4 In your opinion, how important is a debriefing session after an OB Alert?		
Important	11	47.0%
Very important	3	13.0%
Q-5 Have you ever experienced a debriefing session after an OB Alert?		
No answer	9	39.0%
Yes	5	21.0%
No	9	39.0%
Q-6 If yes, how soon was the debriefing session completed?		
No answer	14	60.0%
Immediately	3	13.0%
At the end of the shift	1	4.3%
1-3 days	4	17.0%
1 week	1	4.3%
Q-7 In your opinion how soon should a debriefing session be held after an OB Alert?		
No answer	9	39.0%
Immediately	9	39.0%

Variables	N	Frequency (Valid %)
1 day after COI	5	21.0%
Q-8 What barriers do you believe prevent debriefing sessions from being completed after an OB Alert?	Results described within the paper	
Q-9 Share any comments or stories related to compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, or secondary traumatic stress?	No answers received	

Note. N=23

Figure 9

Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey Terms Used As Barriers to Debriefing

Note. The four most frequently used phrases: Lack of time, increased patient acuity level, other patient assignments, and limited staff were.

Post-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey

During this phase of this project the 213 participants who were presently working at the project facility were decreased by 50 or more. The author was informed the absences occurred due to leave of absences, both for illness and COVID-19 reasons. Of the 213 participants invited, 12 completed the survey, for a response rate of 5.6% (12/213). Descriptive statistics were used to develop the following frequency table (Table 2). The first question in the post-implementation

debriefing satisfaction survey asked: “How many OB Alerts did you experience?” Of those who responded to the survey four (33.0%) did not experience an OB Alert and two (16.7%) experienced two OB Alerts. The next question identified how many of those OB Alerts completed an immediate debriefing session. Of the twelve respondents, three of the OB Alerts were reported to have a debriefing session and eight (66.7%) of the participants did not respond to this question. Of those respondents who experienced an OB Alert, one (8.3%) was done at the end of the shift, two were done immediately (16.7%), and four (33.3%) reported to not have had a debriefing at all. The majority of responders believed that debriefing sessions should be held at the “end of the shift” (41.7%). The fifth question was an open-ended question to assess what barriers continued to be perceived by the participants. The most frequently used words were used to design a word cloud with the largest words representing the most frequently used words and the smaller words less utilized. The common themes related to the barriers preventing debriefing session were patient acuity and obligations, lack of time, management restrictions, charting and limited staff (Figure 10). Respondents believe that debriefing sessions are “very important” (58.3%) after an OB Alert. If a debriefing is held after an OB Alert, respondents believe it can decrease stress associated with future OB Alert participation “most of the time”(33.3%) and “Sometime/Occasionally” (33.3%). Lastly, of those who responded to the survey, 75% believe that by doing an immediate debriefing after an OB Alert, satisfaction can improve in future debriefing experiences. No responses were given for the last open-ended question to share comments or stories on CS, CF, BO, or STS.

Table 2*Post-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey*

Variables	N	Frequency (Valid %)
Q-1 How many OB Alerts did you experience during the implementation period?		
No answer	5	41%
none	4	33.%
1	1	8.%
2	2	16.%
Q-2 How many of those OB Alerts had a post immediate debriefing session?		
No answer	8	66.%
none	3	25.%
1	1	8.%
Q-3 How soon after an OB Alert was a debriefing session held?		
No answer	5	41.%
Immediate	2	16.%
At the end of the shift	1	8.%
1 day later	0	0
One was not held	4	33.%
Q-4 In your opinion, how soon should a debriefing session be held after an OB Alert?		
No answer	4	33.%
Immediately	3	25.%
At the end of the shift	5	41.%
1 week later	0	0
Q-5 What barriers do you believe prevent debriefing from occurring after an OB Alert? Open ended question	==	==
Q-6 In your opinion, how important is a debriefing session after an OB Alert?		
No answer	2	16.%
Very Important	7	58.%
Important	1	8.3%
Somewhat/Slightly Important	2	16.%
Not at all important	0	0
Q-7 Does immediate debriefing after an OB Alert decrease stress associated with participation in OB Alerts?		
No answer	2	16.%
All the time	2	16.%
Most of the time	4	33.%

Variables	N	Frequency (Valid %)
Sometimes/Occasionally	4	33.0%
Q-8 Do you feel immediate debriefing after an OB Alert improves satisfaction with the debriefing experience?		
No answer	2	16.0%
yes	9	75.0%
no	1	8.0%
Q-9 Please share any comments or stories related to CS, CF, or STS. (open ended question)	==	==

Note. N=12

Figure 10

Post-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey Terms Used as Barriers to Debriefing

Note. Nurse, staff, and patient acuity were the three most frequently used words.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to refine the debriefing process used at the project facility by identifying the causes for incomplete or lack of debriefing sessions after an OB Alert. Through the process of the modified Iowa Model, the debriefing process improved by consolidating the debriefing tool to one page. This increased compliance after an OB Alert throughout the QI project time frame which was due to the ease of use and streamlining of information required. Furthermore, the ProQOL 5 was used to identify baseline levels of CS, and CF and the debriefing process satisfaction survey was used to identify barriers to the debriefing process. Education was conducted remotely due to social distancing requirements for the pandemic. The CS was at a high level at the beginning of the project and was sustained, as reported on the pre- and post-ProQOL 5 scores.

The Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey revealed that participants felt their employer helped them cope with the stress associated “most of the time” with OB Alerts 26.1%. In addition, both surveys showed that although a debriefing was offered “some of the time” after an OB Alert, the majority of the respondents believed this process was “important” and “very important.” This shows that the debriefing tool is valued by the staff and has shown to have positive benefits. As such, utilizing a debriefing tool after a critical incident can improve teamwork, communication and offer support to everyone involved (Kleiner et al., 2014; Corbett et al., 2012). Both surveys revealed that a debriefing should be held immediately after a COI or at the end of the shift. When debriefings are delayed, everyone involved can be affected and delays may lead to CF and STS (Kelly et al., 2017). Furthermore, participants reported that having an immediate debriefing after a COI helped to decrease the stress related to participating

in an OB Alert. The reported barriers to completing a debriefing after a COI included acuity of the patients, limited staffing, time constraints, and having other patients to care for.

The key findings of this project were that debriefing continues to be considered a key component when addressing COIs for the mental health of nurses. This is based on the participants' responses to the open-ended question which asked them to identify barriers to carrying out a debriefing process. When nurses are denied the opportunity to debrief, there is a possibility of increasing the emotional toll it can have on their mental well-being (Caine & Bagdasarian, 2003; McNamara et al., 2017).

Limitations and Strengths

The project had several limitations in administration and implementation. First, the project author sent out 213 emails to staff to participate in the project; however, only 36 surveys were returned. Next, the project was also delayed due to changes in administration at the project facility. The director retired and a new director was installed, who had many responsibilities associated with the transition. Once she was established, the project moved forward. This transition added a delay of approximately three weeks. During this time, the COVID-19 pandemic was surging, and nurses' ratios and census increased. This created an increased work demand, which distracted nurses from participating in the project. There were nurses who were also on leave due to medical reasons, which increased during the pandemic from 30 to 50 nurses. Lastly, there were two open-ended questions; however, participants only answered the first question and not the second question. The second question asked participants to identify any additional information they would like to share, and no participants shared. This question was meant to provide an opportunity for the participants to share additional information not gathered

by the survey. The lack of response to the second question may be an indication of the completeness of the survey.

The project had many strengths associated with the benefits of debriefing and its ability to mitigate CF and STS. This project was able to improve the debriefing process providing additional assistance and overall support for those involved in COIs. By continuing the quarterly assessments, adjustments can be made to promote communication, collaboration, and empowerment of the healthcare team.

Recommendations

As a result of the project, there are several recommendations that can be proposed. The project highlights the need for education regarding CS, CF, STS, and the importance of debriefing. In addition, it is vital that quarterly assessments of completed debriefings be conducted to encourage self-care and sustain the current CS levels. It is also recommended that access to additional resources be readily available to nurses after a COI. This access will help to ensure that nurses are cared for emotionally in a highly emotional field. Discussing scenarios and shared experiences in an informal manner with the addition of education helps to increase the sustainability of this improved debriefing process.

Further research is needed using a larger sample size in the areas of COI, so that the findings can be generalized to other settings within the facility which also experience critical incidents. The use of the refined debriefing process should be further examined to continue to streamline it for efficiency.

Conclusion

Ultimately, this QI project provided nurses in the obstetrical unit a debriefing process that was easily implemented and followed, while identifying their mental well-being. The staff coordinators were essential in this project by encouraging staff to complete the debriefing form and surveys. The responses also helped this author identify common themes among nurses. By collaborating with administration, the author plans to review the issues that nurses felt were reasons debriefings are not being completed. By doing so, we can work to maintain the nurses' compassion satisfaction, improve patient care, and decrease the risk of compassion fatigue.

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Appendix A

Permission to Use and/or Reproduce The IOWA Model (2015)

Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <noreply@qemailserver.com>
Sat 2/29/2020 7:48 AM

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[The Iowa Model Revised \(2015\)](#)

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Citation: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182.
doi:10.1111/wvn.12223.

In written material, please add the following statement:

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Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

Appendix B

Permission to Use / Copy ProQOL Measure

ProQOL Office <noreply@surveygizmo.com>
Sat 3/7/2020 12:15 PM
To: You

Thank you for your interest in the ProQOL.

The ProQOL measure may be freely copied and used, without individualized permission from the ProQOL office, as long as:

- (a) You credit The Center for Victims of Torture and provide a link to www.ProQOL.org;
- (b) It is not sold; and
- (c) No changes are made, other than creating or using a translation, and/or replacing "[helper]" with a more specific term such as "nurse."

Because you have agreed that your use of the ProQOL follows the above criteria, the ProQOL Office at the Center for Victims of Torture grants you permission to use the ProQOL. Your recorded request is attached here as a PDF.

If you have any questions or comments, you can contact us at proqol@cvt.org. Note that unfortunately our capacity is quite limited, as this is a volunteer-run effort, but we will do what we can to respond within a couple of weeks.

Thank you!

The ProQOL Office
at The Center for Victims of Torture
proqol@cvt.org

Appendix C
IRB Approval Letter

██████████ <no-reply@irbnet.org>

Mon 9/28/2020 5:07 PM

Please note that California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has taken the following action on IRBNet:

Project Title: [1611219-1] Improving the Critical Obstetrical Debriefing Process: A Quality Improvement Project

Principal Investigator: Cinthya Sotelo, DNP

Submission Type: New Project

Date Submitted: July 21, 2020

Action: APPROVED

Effective Date: September 28, 2020

Review Type: Exempt Review

Should you have any questions you may contact ██████████ at irb3@calstatela.edu.

Thank you,
The IRBNet Support Team

Appendix D

Pre- and Post-Professional Quality of Life Scale 5 (PROQOL 5)

COMPASSION SATISFACTION AND COMPASSION FATIGUE (PROQOL VERSION 5 (2009))

When you help people, you have direct contact with their lives. As you may have found, your compassion for those you help can affect you in positive and negative ways. Below are some questions and your experiences, both positive and negative, as a healthcare provider. Consider each of the following questions about you and your current work situation. Select the number that honestly reflects how frequently you experienced these things in the last 30 days.

1 = Never	2 = Rarely	3 = Sometimes	4 = Often	5 = Very Often	
___ 1.					I am happy.
___ 2.					I am preoccupied with more than one person I help.
___ 3.					I get satisfaction from being able to help people.
___ 4.					I feel connected to others.
___ 5.					I jump or am startled by unexpected sounds.
___ 6.					I feel invigorated after working with those I help.
___ 7.					I find it difficult to separate my personal life from my life as a helper.
___ 8.					I am not as productive at work because I am losing sleep over traumatic experiences of a person I help.
___ 9.					I think that I might have been affected by the traumatic stress of those I help.
___ 10.					I feel trapped by my job as a healthcare provider.
___ 11.					Because of my helping, I have felt "on edge" about various things.
___ 12.					I like my work as a healthcare provider.
___ 13.					I feel depressed because of the traumatic experiences of the people I help.
___ 14.					I feel as though I am experiencing the trauma of someone I have helped.
___ 15.					I have beliefs that sustain me.
___ 16.					I am pleased with how I am able to keep up with helping techniques and protocols.
___ 17.					I am the person I always wanted to be.
___ 18.					My work makes me feel satisfied.
___ 19.					I feel worn out because of my work as a healthcare provider.
___ 20.					I have happy thoughts and feelings about those I help and how I could help them.
___ 21.					I feel overwhelmed because my case workload seems endless.
___ 22.					I believe I can make a difference through my work.
___ 23.					I avoid certain activities or situations because they remind of frightening experiences of the people I help.
___ 24.					I am proud of what I can do to help.
___ 25.					As a result of my helping, I have intrusive, frightening thoughts.
___ 26.					I "feel bogged down" by the system.
___ 27.					I have thoughts that I am a "success" as a helper.
___ 28.					I can't recall important parts of my work with trauma victims.
___ 29.					I am a very caring person.
___ 30.					I am happy that I chose to do this work.

YOUR SCORES ON THE PROQOL: PROFESSIONAL QUALITY OF LIFE SCREENING

Based on your responses, place your personal scores below. If you have any concerns, you should discuss them with a physical or mental health care professional.

Compassion Satisfaction _____

Compassion satisfaction is about the pleasure you derive from being able to do your work well. For example, you may feel like it is a pleasure to help others through your work. You may feel positively about your colleagues or your ability to contribute to the work setting or even the greater good of society. Higher scores on this scale represent a greater satisfaction related to your ability to be an effective caregiver in your job.

If you are in the higher range, you probably derive a good deal of professional satisfaction from your position. If your scores are below 23, you may either find problems with your job, or there may be some other reason ---for example, you might derive your satisfaction from activities other than your job. (Alpha scale reliability 0.88)

Burnout _____

Most people have an intuitive idea of what burnout is. From the research perspective, burnout is one of the elements of Compassion Fatigue (CF). It is associated with feelings of hopelessness and difficulties in dealing with work or in doing your job effectively. These negative feelings usually have a gradual onset. They can reflect the feeling that your efforts make no difference, or they can be associated with a very high workload or a non-supportive work environment. Higher scores on this scale mean that you are at higher risk for burnout.

If your score is below 23, this probably reflects positive feelings about your ability to be effective in your work. If you score about 41, you may wish to think about what at work makes you feel like you are not effective in your position. Your score may reflect your mood; perhaps you were having a “bad day” or are in need of some time off. If the high score persists or if it is reflective of other worries, it may be a cause for concern, (Alpha scale reliability 0.75)

Secondary Traumatic Stress _____

The second component of Compassion Fatigue (CF) is secondary traumatic stress (STS). It is about your work related, secondary exposure to extremely or traumatically stressful events. Developing problems due to exposure to others trauma is somewhat rare but does happen to many who care for those who have experienced extremely or traumatically stressful events. For example, you may repeatedly hear stories about the traumatic things that happen to other people, commonly called Vicarious Traumatization. If your work puts you directly in the path of danger, for example, field work in a war or area of civil violence, this is not secondary exposure; your exposure is primary. However, if you are exposed to others’ traumatic events as a result of your work, for example, as a therapist or an emergency worker, this is secondary exposure. The symptoms of STS are usually rapid in onset and associated with a particular event. They may include being afraid, having difficulty sleeping, having images of the upsetting event pop into your mind, or avoiding things that remind you of the event.

If your score is 41, you may want to take some time to think about what at work may be frightening to you or if there is some other reason for the elevated score. While higher scores do not mean that you do have a problem, they are an indication that you may want to examine how you feel about your work environment. You may wish to discuss this with your supervisor, a colleague, or a health care professional. (Alpha scale reliability 0.81).

WHAT IS MY SCORE AND WHAT DOES IT MEAN?

In this section, you will score your test, so you understand the interpretation for you. To find your score on each section, total the questions listed on the left and then find your score in the table on the right of the section.

Compassion Satisfaction Scale

Copy your rating on each of these Questions on this table and add them up. When you have added them up you can find your score on the table to the right.

- 3. _____
- 6. _____
- 12. _____
- 16. _____
- 18. _____
- 20. _____
- 22. _____
- 24. _____
- 27. _____
- 30. _____
- Total:** _____

The Sum of my Compassion Satisfaction questions is	And my Compassion Satisfaction level is
22 or less	Low
Between 23-41	Moderate
42 or more	High

Burnout Scale

On the burnout scale you will need to take an extra step. Starred items are “reversed score.” If you scored the item 1 writes a 5 beside it. The reason we ask you to reverse the score is because scientifically the measure works better when these questions are asked in a positive way though they can tell us more about their negative form. For example, question 1. “I am happy” tells us more about

- *1. _____ = _____
- *4. _____ = _____
- 8. _____ = _____
- 10. _____
- *15. _____ = _____
- *17. _____ = _____
- 19. _____
- 21. _____
- 26. _____
- *29. _____ = _____
- Total:** _____

The Sum of my Burnout Questions is	And my Burnout level is
22 or less	Low
Between 23-41	Moderate
42 or more	High

You Wrote	Change to
	5
2	4
3	3
4	2
5	1

the effects of helping when you are not happy so you reverse the score.

The Sum of my secondary Trauma questions is	And my Secondary Traumatic Stress level is
--	---

Secondary Traumatic Stress Scale

Just like you did on Compassion Satisfaction copy your rating on each of these questions on to this table and add them up. When you have added them you can find your score on the table to the right

- 2. _____
- 5. _____
- 7. _____
- 9. _____
- 11. _____
- 13. _____
- 14. _____
- 23. _____
- 25. _____
- 28. _____

22 or less	Low
Between 23-41	Moderate
42 or more	High

B. Hudnall Stamm, 2009-2012. Professional Quality of Life: Compassion Satisfaction and Fatigue Version 5 (ProQOL). www.proqol.org.

Appendix E

Previous Debriefing Form 1

CMQCC - California Partnership for Maternal Safety OBSTETRIC HEMORRHAGE DEBRIEF FORM

The debrief form provides an opportunity for obstetric service teams to review the sequence of events, successes and barriers to a swift and coordinated response to obstetric hemorrhage.

Goal: Debrief all obstetric hemorrhages (up to five) per month that include the following triggers:

- 1000 (1500) ml blood loss – Stage 2 (3) hemorrhage (*will depend on the frequency of events at your hospital, to be determined by your own institution*)
- Administration of **second** dose of any uterotonic medication (methergine, hemabate, misoprostol)
- Use of uterine tamponade balloon or B-lynch suture
- Administration of blood products

Instructions: Complete debrief form as soon as possible after event as described above. During debrief, obtain input from as many participants as possible.

Date:

Time:

Submitted by:

RECOGNITION	
Was patient assigned a hemorrhage risk? <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Not done	Volume of Blood Lost _____ Method: <input type="checkbox"/> Formal quantification <input type="checkbox"/> Visual estimation <input type="checkbox"/> Both
RESPONSE	
Supplies/cart: Identify opportunities for improvement: <input type="checkbox"/> Appropriate supplies available <input type="checkbox"/> Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Medications <input type="checkbox"/> Blood products <input type="checkbox"/> Procedure <input type="checkbox"/> Device(s) working properly? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Other issues?:	Blood products Available without delay? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Adequate blood product volume available? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
TEAMWORK	
Timely Team response? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
All roles filled? <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Physician <input type="checkbox"/> Primary Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Charge Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Documentation <input type="checkbox"/> Runner <input type="checkbox"/> Anesthesia	
Role clarity? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Was there a clear leader? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	
Was there clear communication? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	

Participants (Name, Role):

Issue(s) or Recommendation(s)

Previous Debriefing Form 2

Date _____ Patient Room _____ Station _____

OB Alert Called at: _____ Time Patient arrived in OR _____

Primary Indication / FHR Tracing Pattern:				Diagnosis / Reason for Admission:
Team Members Responding:				OR Times:
Discipline Name	Arrival Time	Discipline Name	Arrival Time	Patient on OR Table
Primary Nurse:		OR Assigned RN:		Incision Time:
Triage RN:		Clinical Supervisor		Delivery:
In-House OB:		NICU Transport Team:		Apgar Score: 1min _____ 5 min _____ 10 min _____
Attending OB:		OR Circulating RN:		
Anesthesia:				Additional comments:

Date: _____ Time: _____ Labor RN: _____ Signature: _____

Date: _____ Time: _____ Delivery RN: _____ Signature: _____

Patient Sticker Below

This is NOT part of the patient's chart

Appendix F

Consolidated Debriefing Form

Patient Label

LDRP Significant Events Debrief Form

The debrief form provides an opportunity for obstetric service teams to review the sequence of events, successes and barriers to a swift and coordinated response to any unanticipated obstetric or neonatal event.

Instructions: Complete debrief form as soon as possible after event as described above. During debrief, obtain input from as many participants as possible.

Date:

Time:

Submitted by:

Type of Alert Called	Reason for Calling Alert	
<input type="checkbox"/> OB Alert	<input type="checkbox"/> PP Hemorrhage	Time Alert was Called: _____
<input type="checkbox"/> Code Crimson	<input type="checkbox"/> Maternal Distress	Outcome:
<input type="checkbox"/> Rapid Response	<input type="checkbox"/> Fetal Distress	____ Remain in LDR ____ To OR
<input type="checkbox"/> Code Blue	<input type="checkbox"/> Eclamptic Seizure	____ FHR Tracing resolved ____ to NICU
<input type="checkbox"/> Code White	<input type="checkbox"/> Maternal Arrest	Transferred to: _____
<input type="checkbox"/> Gold Alert	<input type="checkbox"/> Newborn Arrest	Delivery: ____ Vag ____ C/S
<input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____	<input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____	Apgars: ____/____/____
_____	_____	Comments: _____
_____	_____	_____
If Code Crimson or Postpartum Hemorrhage Identified Recognition: Was Patient Assigned a Hemorrhage Risk? <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Not Done Volume of Blood Loss: _____ Method: <input type="checkbox"/> QBL <input type="checkbox"/> EBL		If New Onset Severe Hypertension/Preeclampsia Identified Recognition: Were there any delays in <input type="checkbox"/> Recognition? <input type="checkbox"/> Notification? Comments: _____
Response: Supplies/Cart: Opportunities for Improvement: <input type="checkbox"/> Appropriate Supplies Available <input type="checkbox"/> Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Medications <input type="checkbox"/> Blood Products <input type="checkbox"/> Procedure <input type="checkbox"/> Devices working properly: Y N Blood Products: Available without Delay? <input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N Adequate Blood Volume Available? <input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N Comments: _____		Response: Time Severe Hypertension Identified: _____ Time 1 st line Hypertensive Given: _____ Medication Given: _____ # of Doses needed to reach target BP: _____ Supplies: Opportunities for Improvement: <input type="checkbox"/> Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Medication <input type="checkbox"/> Other issues: _____
If other Alert Identified Recognition: Were there any delays in: <input type="checkbox"/> Recognition? <input type="checkbox"/> Notification? Opportunities for Improvement: <input type="checkbox"/> Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Medications <input type="checkbox"/> Process Other Issues: _____ Comments: _____		Teamwork Clear closed loop communication? <input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N Timely Team Management? <input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N Clear Documentation? <input type="checkbox"/> Y <input type="checkbox"/> N All Roles Filled? <input type="checkbox"/> Primary MD <input type="checkbox"/> Primary RN <input type="checkbox"/> Charge RN <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary RN <input type="checkbox"/> Anesthesia Other Roles present: _____

Not part of the Patient's Chart, please turn in to Supervisor after Debrief.

Patient Label

LDRP Significant Events Debrief Form

Name/Title	Role/Department

Issues/Recommendations/Pertinent Information:

Cerner charting leading to event completed?: Y N Incident Report Done? Y N

Was group debrief done? Y N Date/Time of Debrief: _____

Not part of the Patient's Chart, please turn in to Supervisor after Debrief.

Appendix G

Promotion Posters 1 and 2

Professional Quality of Life

Compassion
Satisfaction
Positive
aspects of working as a
health care professional

Compassion
Fatigue
Negative
aspects of working as a
health
care professional

Burnout
Inefficacy
and feeling overwhelmed

Work-related
traumatic stress
Primary
traumatic stress direct
target of an event

Secondary
traumatic exposure to
event due to a
relationship with the
primary person

Beth Hudnall, 2009
www.ProQOL.org

Professional Quality of Life

**The ProQOL measures
Compassion Satisfaction
and Compassion Fatigue**

**A 30 item self-report
measure of the positive
and negative aspects of
caring**

**Compassion Fatigue has two subscales: Burnout
and Secondary Trauma**

**The ProQOL can help you plan
where to put your energy to
increase your resilience**

Beth Hudnall Stamm, 2009,
www.ProQOL.org

APPENDIX H

Cover Letter for Participant Consent

Hello Everyone,

You are invited to take part in a quality improvement project conducted by Yvette Ambroze, FNP-C, a DNP student at California State University, Los Angeles/Fullerton Consortium. In this study we hope to modify the debriefing process and improve compassion satisfaction and compassion fatigue among nurses. Critical Obstetrical Incidents (COI) can cause burnout, secondary traumatic stress, and compassion fatigue which can lead to high turnover among nurses. A debriefing process that supports teamwork, can help with potential safety threats, supply coping skills, and provide support to nurses who experience a COI. You are asked to voluntarily participate in this study because you are part of the healthcare team. We hope this will lead to reasonably expected benefits to this subject.

I kindly request that you spend approximately 10-15 minutes completing the ProQOL survey that is being sent to you via the attached link. The survey contains questions regarding the positive and negative aspects of doing one's job and how it influences one's professional quality of life. This project will take place over a 2-3-month period and will involve this pre-ProQOL survey to be completed and a post--ProQOL survey that will be completed at the end of the project period. Also, there will be pre- and post-implementation debriefing satisfaction survey that will be sent at a later time. There will be no financial compensation for participation.

By completing the survey, you indicate that you have read this form and consent to voluntarily participate in the study. All responses are confidential. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time.

Please print page 4 of the consent forms (I have attached page 4 separately making it easier to print in the attached section) and place in Coordinator's office she will place your consent in a designated folder.

Here is the link to participate in the ProQOL survey.

http://fullerton.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_4I3Y2xsOOaIzH5r

Thank you in advance for your participation.

If you have any questions you can contact me at [REDACTED] or [REDACTED].
Yvette Ambroze, FNP-C

Appendix I

Pre-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey

Question	All the time	Most of the Time	Sometimes	Occasionally	Never
How often do you experience OB Alerts at work?					
Do you feel your employer helps you cope with stress associated with OB Alerts?					

Question	All the time	Most of the Time	Sometimes	Occasionally	Never
Does your employer offer debriefing sessions after an OB Alert					

Question	Very Important	Important	Somewhat Important	Slightly	Not Important
In your opinion, how important is a debriefing session after an OB Alert?					

Have you ever experienced a debriefing session after an OB Alert? Yes ____ No ____

Question	Immediately	At the end of the shift	1-3 days	1-week	2-weeks
If yes, how soon was the debriefing					

session completed?					
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In your opinion, how soon should a debriefing session be held after an OB Alert.

1. Immediately? 3. 1 day after?

2. At the end of the shift? 4. 1 week later?

What barriers do you believe prevent debriefing sessions from being completed after an OB Alert?

Appendix J**Post-Implementation Debriefing Satisfaction Survey**

Question	None	1	2	3	4+
How many OB Alerts did you experience at work during the implementation period?					
How many of those OB Alerts had a post immediate debriefing session?					

Question	Immediate	At the end of the shift	1 day later	One was not held
How soon after an OB Alert was a debriefing session held?				
Question	Immediate	At the end of the shift	1 day later	1 week later
In your opinion, how soon should a debriefing session be held after an OB Alert?				

What barriers do you believe prevent debriefing from occurring after an OB Alert?

Question	Very Important	Important	Somewhat Important	Slightly Important	Not Important
How important is a debriefing session after an OB Alert?					

Question	All the Time	Most of the Time	Sometimes	Occasionally	Never
Does immediate debriefing after an OB Alert decrease stress associated with participation in OB Alerts?					
Does immediate debriefing after OB Alerts improve satisfaction with debriefing experience?					

